

Optical waveguides based upon a gauge field

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Photons are neutral particles, thus they are not affected by magnetic fields. Nonetheless, light propagation under the action of an effective magnetic field has been demonstrated [1,2]. This counter-intuitive result can be grasped by thinking in terms of gauge fields, that is, a point-wise change of the framework. Synthetic magnetic fields have been generated by introducing phase shifts in coupled resonators [1] or by longitudinal modulation of arrays of coupled waveguides [2]. Intuitively, an inhomogeneous gauge field can induce a transverse gradient in the optical phase such that it compensates the spreading by diffraction, eventually forming an optical waveguide. As a matter of fact, in discrete systems this type of light trapping has been first theoretically predicted in coupled resonators [3], and very recently experimentally demonstrated in femtosecond-written waveguides [4]. Here, we propose a new method to realize gauge-based continuous waveguides using a longitudinally periodic modulation of the refractive index [5] featuring a point-wise shift; specifically, the phase of the periodic modulation varies along the cross-section of the waveguide and represents the gauge field in our proposal.

We consider a periodic modulation of the refractive index along the propagation distance z , $\Delta n(x, z) = V(x)f(z)$ with $f(z) = f(z + \Lambda)$. The average value of the refractive index is vanishing ($\int_0^\Lambda n(x, z) dz = 0$), and the amplitude of the modulation $V(x)$ varies along the waveguide cross-section, i.e., x . An effective photonic potential (taken proportional to $-\Delta n$) emerges due to the Kapitza effect [5]. Such a potential is proportional to the square of the transverse derivative of the refractive index, $V_{\text{eff}} \propto (\partial_x V)^2$. If an inhomogeneous transverse delay is introduced by setting $f = f[z - \tau(x)]$, V_{eff} then includes an additional term proportional to the square of the transverse derivative of the delay, i.e., $\propto (\partial_x \tau)^2$. To focus on the gauge-induced confinement, we consider a flat-top function for $V(x)$. Light is trapped when the potential is minimum around the origin, thus we need a distribution for $\tau(x)$ such that the absolute value of the first derivative $|\partial_x \tau|$ undergoes a global minimum around the origin. We chose a sine hyperbolic function, the corresponding distribution of Δn being plotted in Fig. 1(a). The existence of light trapping is then confirmed by using numerical simulations based upon a BPM, shown in Fig. 1(b).

Fig. 1 (a) Refractive index $\Delta n(x, z)$ when $f(z)$ is sinusoidal and $\tau = \phi_0 [\Lambda / (2\pi)] \sinh(x/l)$ with $l = 5 \mu\text{m}$, $\phi_0 = 0.05\pi$ and period $\Lambda = 10 \mu\text{m}$. (b) Simulations of the intensity distribution versus ϕ_0 for the otherwise identical delay when $\max(V) = 0.5$ for an input Gaussian beam of waist $5 \mu\text{m}$ at $\lambda = 1 \mu\text{m}$. The propagation distance corresponds to 100 Rayleigh lengths.

Summarizing, we theoretically and numerically introduced a novel type of waveguides based upon gauge confinement in periodic structures. Our results can find applications e.g. in Silicon photonics, or in designing new types of Bragg reflectors capable to mold the optical field also in the transverse direction.

References

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